

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN QWL AND ORGANIZATIONAL COMMITMENT AMONGST SALES REPRESENTATIVES OF AUTOMOBILE INDUSTRY

Dr. Shalini A

Assistant Professor, Commerce Department, GFGC, Chamarajanagara, India

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18162145>

Published Date: 06-January-2026

Abstract: Employee satisfaction and quality of work life directly affect company's ability to serve its customers. Determining the quality of work life of employees is an important consideration for employers, interested in improving employees' job satisfaction and commitment. Committed employees play a vital role in success of a business. In this regard, quality of work life is one of the important issue which affects organisational commitment of employees. Therefore it is essential to investigate the relationship between quality of work life and organisational commitment of sales representatives in automobile industry. The aim of this paper is to investigate relationship between QWL and Organizational Commitment amongst sales representatives in marketing of light motor vehicles. . The study found that there is positive relationship exists between quality of work life and organizational commitment.

Keywords: Automobile Industry, Organisational Commitment, Quality of Work Life, Relationship, Sales Representatives.

1. INTRODUCTION

The heart of business success lies in its marketing. Marketing is a process by which a product or service is introduced and promoted to potential customers. The marketing covers advertising, public relations, promotions and sales. Among these, selling is at the core of any business. Sales force is the backbone of all the businesses all over the world. Therefore, the people who do the selling are more important than any other group in the organisation. Despite their importance, most of the business strategies attribute least priority to the sales staff of the company. This leads to lower job satisfaction and sales performance, decreased organisational commitment and more turnovers. Therefore, it is very essential for an organisation to retain sales representatives. A sales representative is a person who sells products on behalf of a company. Sales representatives work with customers to find what they want, create solutions and ensure a smooth sales process.

The Automobile industry is a wide range of companies and organisations involved in the design, development, manufacturing, marketing and selling of motor vehicles. The Indian automobile industry includes two-wheelers, trucks, cars, buses and three wheelers which play a crucial role in growth of the Indian economy. The success and growth of automobile industry depends on sales. Sales people can make or break a business, depending on their level of professionalism, commitment and integrity. Sales representative's satisfaction and quality of work life directly affect company's ability to serve its customers. Quality of work life creates a culture of work commitment, so as to ensure higher productivity and job satisfaction. . Determining the quality of work life of employees is an important consideration for employers, interested in improving employees' job satisfaction and commitment.

2. QUALITY OF WORK LIFE

The term “quality of work life” (QWL) originated from the concept of the open socio-technical system designed in the 1970s that helps to ensure autonomy in work, interdependence, and self-involvement with the idea of “best fit” between technology and social organizations. Quality of work life is a comprehensive and expanded program that increases member satisfaction, reinforces their learning with the environment, and helps them to manage change. The aim of many organizations is increasing members’ satisfaction in all levels. However, this is a complex problem, because the separation and determination that what factors relate to QWL is difficult (Seraji, 2006).

Quality of work life is a multi-dimensional construct that needs careful consideration to conceptualise and measure. It can be described as the favourable working environment that supports and promotes satisfaction by providing employees with rewards, job security, career growth opportunities etc.

Davis (1983) defined QWL is the broader spectrum that exemplifies all the researched factors like satisfaction, commitment, turnover, compensation, relationship management, organisation culture etc.

Walton (1973) defined the QWL as the personnel reaction to work; especially its essential outcome in relation to job needs satisfaction and psychological health.

Nadler and Lawler defines QWL as “a way of thinking about people, work and organisations, its distinctive elements are (i) a concern about the impact of work on people as well as on organisational effectiveness, and (ii) the idea of participation in organisational problem-solving and decision making.”

From the above definitions QWL can be said to be all the original inputs which aim at improving the employees’ satisfaction and enhancing organisational effectiveness. It is nothing but having a work environment where employees’ activities become more important. The QWL encompasses the sum of total healthy experience of individual’s experience in various facets of the work life or life at work.

3. LITERATURE REVIEW

Various studies on Quality of work life and Sales Representatives have been carried on in India and abroad. The present literature review will only cover the concepts related with dimensions of quality of work life and studies related with sales representatives.

Macy and Mirvis (1976) assessed the quality of working life on the basis of factors such as absenteeism, tardiness, turnover, work stoppages, strikes, productivity, product or service quality, grievances, accidents and job-related illness, unscheduled downtime and unaccounted for inventory, material, and supply utilization variances. Authors describe the development and implementation of a standardized set of definitions, measures, and costing methods for behavioural outcomes. The study found that satisfied employees are more likely to work more effectively and remain in the organisation.

Mark W. Johnston et al (1987) investigated patterns of change among new salespeople’s organizational commitment and job satisfaction in order to gain insights into attitudinal differences which may be expected to exist between stayers and leavers during their first year with the organization by considering five dimensions [Pay satisfaction, Promotion satisfaction, Supervisor satisfaction, Work satisfaction, Co-worker satisfaction] of job satisfaction as they related to turnover among new salespeople and they found that differences exist between stayers and leavers with respect to these variables very early in their job tenure.

Normala and Daud (2010) investigated the relationship between quality of work life and organizational commitment among a sample of employees in Malaysia by using seven QWL variables namely growth and development, participation, physical environment, supervision, pay and benefits and social relevance. They found that there was a relationship between QWL and organizational commitment.

G. Jagadish Chandran (2007) conducted an empirical study of quality of work life in the industrial estates of Kerala. The study was conducted in two stages. In the first stage the researcher collected secondary data from the published sources like publications and in the second stage, primary data were collected by a field survey. The researcher found that Richard Walton’s eight point factors can be considered as the most important factors responsible for quality of work life. The research concluded that the level of the quality of work life of employees working in industrial estates of Kerala is below average. The study suggested that Slight increase in the compensation, creation of the feeling that management is always concerned with workers personal problems, provision of promotion opportunities wherever possible, minimum facilities for cultural programmes etc. can change the attitude of the workers positively and can increase the level of quality of work life without much cost to the entrepreneurs.

Kayalvizhi (2007) conducted a study on job satisfaction, organisational commitment and quality of work life among private hospital nurses in Vellore district, Tamil Nadu. The study was conducted in private hospitals located in the District of Vellore, during a period of 8 months from May 2005 to December 2005 through Field survey. Focus of the study was to determine the impact of job satisfaction, organizational commitment and perceived Quality of work life, on the intention of qualified staff Nurses employed in private hospitals to stay with or quit the work setting. The results of the study showed that the nurses were highly dissatisfied with their jobs and only satisfactory aspect with regard to the nurses' perception on quality of work life dimension was with the grievance redressal process done in the organizations.

M. Anand, and D. Arora, (2009), Organizational commitment was found to have a positive and direct relationship in terms of QWL dimensions in sectors like banking, food and education industry.

4. SCOPE OF THE STUDY

The study pertains to the dimension of QWL, in general and QWL amongst sales representatives in marketing of light motor vehicles, in specific. Although, QWL is essential for all type of organizations this study is confined only to the study of QWL amongst sales representatives in marketing of light motor vehicles. This study considers sales representatives of automobile industry in Karnataka. A perceptual study of Sales Representatives will be carried out using a questionnaire to study the satisfaction level of quality of work life of sales representatives.

5. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To investigate the relationship between QWL and Organizational Commitment amongst sales representatives in marketing of light motor vehicles.
- To suggest measures to improve QWL of sales representatives working in automobile industry.

5.1 Hypothesis

Committed employees play a vital role in success of a business. In this regard, quality of work life is one of the important issue which affects organisational commitment of employees. Therefore it is essential to investigate the relationship between quality of work life and organisational commitment of sales representatives in automobile industry. To test the relationship between factors of quality of work life and organisational commitment the following hypothesis is framed.

H_0 : There is no significant relationship between quality of work life and organizational commitment.

H_1 : There is significant relationship between quality of work life and organizational commitment.

6. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research design chosen for the study was exploratory and descriptive in nature. Unit of analysis considered for the study is 'individuals' in the capacity of sales representatives working in various automobile industries in Karnataka. The study is based on both primary and secondary data. Primary data was collected with help of self-administered questionnaire from respondents belonging to various age groups, genders, educational levels and experience. The questionnaire focuses on 8 dimensions of quality of work life such as; Adequate and fair compensation, Safe and Healthy Working Conditions, Immediate Opportunity of Use and Develop Human Capacities, Future Opportunity for Continued Growth and Security, Social Integration in Work Organization, Constitutionalism in the Work Organization, Work and the Total Life Space, Social Relevance of Work Life.

This study is an empirical one and is based on a questionnaire survey of sales representatives in marketing of automobiles. Sales representatives were selected as a relevant population, because both working hard and working smart are necessary for effective performance in this profession. The survey was carried out in Karnataka covering Bangalore division, Belgaum division, Mysore division and Gulbarga division. To fulfil the objectives of this study, a random sample 600 sales representatives of automobile industry will be taken at 4% confidence interval. The sample consists of 150 sales representatives from each division of Karnataka.

Based on the literature survey 32 statements were developed to measure quality of work life. Statements of the questionnaire were well structured with 5 point Likert scale ranging from 1 (highly dissatisfied) to 5 (highly satisfied). The reliability test has been conducted for factors of quality of work life. Cronbach's Alpha was used to check the reliability of the scale. The reliability test results show that the questionnaire designed for the present study is reliable with respect to all the factors of quality of work life as alpha coefficients had an acceptable level which is greater than 0.70, which is considered as highly

sufficient. The collected data were analysed by using SPSS and various statistical tests were applied to test the hypothesis such as; descriptive statistics (mean, standard deviation and S.E mean) and independent samples t test were used.

7. ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Organisational commitment is an individual's psychological attachment to the organisation. The present study using three dimensions of organisational commitment conceptualised by Allen and Meyer (1990). They are,

- a) Affective commitment
- b) Continuance commitment
- c) Normative commitment

7.1 Affective Commitment

Affective commitment is employees' positive emotional attachment to the organisation. On the basis of available literatures 4 statements were used and sales representatives' opinions about their positive emotional attachment to the organisation are analysed. In order to check whether these 4 statements are enough or not for measuring affective commitment reliability test has been applied. Since, the Cronbach's Alpha (0.795) is greater than 0.7. It can conclude that the 4 statements selected for evaluation can give more than 70% coverage of the factors and are therefore reliable.

These four statements include,

- i. Positive emotional attachment to the organization
- ii. Believing in organization's goals and values
- iii. A strong sense of belonging to organization
- iv. Feeling organization problems as own problems

Sales representatives' opinion about these four sub variables are tabulated below.

Table 1: Affective Commitment

Sl No	Sub Variables	Highly Disagreed	Disagreed	Not sure	Agreed	Highly Agreed
1	SV1	54 (9%)	98 (16.3%)	134 (22.3%)	229 (38.2%)	85 (14.2%)
2	SV2	88 (14.7%)	57 (9.5%)	161 (26.8%)	208 (34.7%)	86 (14.3%)
3	SV3	102 (17%)	199 (33.2%)	154 (25.7%)	124 (20.7%)	21 (3.5%)
4	SV4	94 (15.7%)	217 (36.2%)	139 (23.2%)	119 (19.8%)	31 (5.2%)

(Source: Primary data)

52.4% sales representatives are agreed with positive emotional attachment to the organisation as an effect of quality of work life prevailing in the organisation. 22.3% of the respondents are not sure about their opinion and 25.3% of the respondents are disagreed with the above statement.

14.7% and 9.5% of the respondents are highly disagreed and agreed respectively with the impact of level of quality of work life in the organisation on their trust in organisations goals and values. On the other hand 14.3% and 34.7% of the respondents are highly agreed and agreed respectively and 26.8% of the respondents are not sure with the above fact.

More than one half (50.2%) of the total respondents are disagreed with the statement a sense of belonging to organisation as a result of level of quality of work life prevailing in the organisation. 25.7% of the respondents are not sure and 24.2% of the respondents are agreed with the above statement.

Regarding feeling organisation problems as own problems as an impact of satisfaction level of quality of work life 51.9% of the respondents are not agreed. 23.2% of the respondents are not sure and 25% of the respondents are agreed with the above fact.

7.2 Continuance Commitment

Continuance commitment is based on weighing up the pros and cons of leaving present organisation. On the basis of available literatures 5 statements were used and sales representatives' opinions about their continuance commitment to the organisation are analysed. In order to check whether these 5 statements are enough or not for measuring continuance commitment reliability test has been applied. Since, the Cronbach's Alpha (0.733) is greater than 0.7. It can conclude that the 5 statements selected for evaluation can give more than 70% coverage of the factors and are therefore reliable.

These five statements include,

- i. Afraid of quitting present job without having another one lined up
- ii. Feeling very hard to leave organization right now
- iii. Quitting present job will disrupt your life
- iv. Staying with organization is a matter of necessity
- v. There is no other option to consider leaving this organization

Sales representatives' opinion above mentioned sub variables of continuance commitment are analysed in the following table:

Table 2: Continuance Commitment

SI No	Sub Variables	Highly Disagreed	Disagreed	Not sure	Agreed	Highly Agreed
1	SV5	0 (0.0%)	35 (5.8%)	54 (9%)	341 (56.8%)	170 (28.3%)
2	SV6	7 (1.2%)	36 (6%)	130 (21.7%)	318 (53%)	109 (18.2%)
3	SV7	8 (1.3%)	57 (9.5%)	106 (17.7%)	224 (37.3%)	205 (34.2%)
4	SV8	26 (4.3%)	95 (15.8%)	226 (37.7%)	205 (34.2%)	48 (8%)
5	SV9	26 (4.3%)	142 (23.7%)	254 (42.3%)	148 (24.7%)	30 (5%)

(Source: Primary data)

The dominant group i.e. 85.1% respondents are agreed with the statement afraid of quitting present job without having another lined up. 9% of the respondents are not sure, only 5.8% of the respondents are disagreed and none of the respondents (0.0%) are highly disagreed with this fact.

Regarding the second statement, feeling very hard to leave organisation right now 71.2% sales representatives are agreed and only 7.2% respondents are disagreed. But 21.7% of the respondents are not sure with the above fact.

Majority of the respondents (71.5%) are agreed with the statement quitting present job will disrupt your life. Only 10.8% of the respondents are disagreed and 17.7% of the respondents are not sure respectively with the above statement.

37.7% of the respondents are not sure in their opinion about the statement staying in the organisation is a matter of necessity. 42.2% of the respondents are agreed and 20.1% of the respondents are not agreed with the above fact.

Regarding the last statement, there is no other option to consider leaving this organisation majority of the respondents are not sure (42.3%). 29.7% of the respondents and 27.7% of the respondents are agreed and disagreed respectively with the above statement.

7.3 Normative Commitment

Normative commitment differs from other two types of organisational commitment. In this, employees feel obliged to work for the organisation for all the things the organisation has done for them. This commitment varies from person to person. On the basis of available literatures 4 statements were used to analyse normative commitment. In order to check whether these 4 statements are enough or not for measuring normative commitment reliability test has been applied. Since, the Cronbach's Alpha (0.737) is greater than 0.7. It can conclude that the 4 statements selected for evaluation can give more than 70% coverage of the factors and are therefore reliable.

These four statements include,

- i. Builds greater loyalty
- ii. Staying with organization
- iii. Bound to the organization goals and expectations
- iv. Feeling guilty to leave the organization

Sales representatives' opinion about these four sub variables are tabulated below:

Table 3: Normative Commitment

Sl No	Sub Variables	Highly Disagreed	Disagreed	Not sure	Agreed	Highly Agreed
1	SV10	58 (9.7%)	95 (15.8%)	161 (26.8%)	203 (33.8%)	83 (13.8%)
2	SV11	72 (12%)	95 (15.8%)	152 (25.3%)	219 (36.5%)	62 (10.3%)
3	SV12	39 (6.5%)	158 (26.3%)	147 (24.5%)	149 (24.8%)	107 (17.8%)
4	SV13	73 (12.2%)	214 (35.7%)	137 (22.8%)	106 (17.7%)	70 (11.7%)

(Source: Primary data)

Table 3 shows that 47.6% of respondents are agreed/highly agreed with the statement quality of work life builds greater loyalty. 24.5% respondents are disagreed/highly disagreed with the above fact and 26.8% of respondents are not sure.

46.8% of the respondents are agreed with the statement staying with organisation as the impact of quality of work life. 25.3% of the respondents are not sure and 27.8% of the respondents are not agreed with the above fact.

42.6% of the respondents are agreed/highly agreed with the statement bound to the organisation goals and expectations as a result of quality of work life prevailing in the organisation. But 32.8% of the respondents are disagreed/highly disagreed and 24.5% of the respondents are not sure about the above statement.

Regarding last statement feeling guilty to leave the organisation as an impact of quality of work life prevailing in the organisation 35.7% are disagreed and 12.2% are highly disagreed. But 22.8% are not sure and 29.4% of respondents are agreed with the above fact.

Table 4: Results of Exploratory Factor Loadings for Organisational Commitment

Sl. No	Dimensions of Organizational Commitment	Variables	Factor Loadings
1	Affective Commitment	Positive emotional attachment to the organization	0.846
2		Believing in organization's goals and values	0.875
3		A strong sense of belonging to organization	0.642
4		Feeling organization problems as own problems	0.621
5	Continuance Commitment	Afraid of quitting present job without having another one lined up	0.862
6		Feeling very hard to leave organization right now	0.850
7		Quitting present job will disrupt your life	0.600
8		Staying with organization is a matter of necessity	0.760
9		There is no other option to consider leaving this organization	0.692
10	Normative Commitment	Builds greater loyalty	0.722
11		Staying with organization	0.891
12		Bound to the organization goals and expectations	0.833
13		Feeling guilty to leave the organization	0.604

(Source: Primary data)

These dimensions explain the features of organisational commitment of employees. Sales representatives were asked to respond a set of 13 statements on a five point Likert scale on the basis of degree of agreement given by them on each statement. Based on the scoring obtained, the total score for each respondent and the average score for each variable were calculated. Scores of the sales representatives whose total scores were between 52 – 65 were placed in “High level of Organisational Commitment” category, scores between 26 – 51 were placed in “Moderate Level of Organisational Commitment” category and scores below 26 were considered in “Low level of Organisational Commitment” category.

Table 5: Correlation Analysis for Significant Relationship between Factors affecting Quality of Work Life and Dimensions of Organisational Commitment

		Affective Commitment	Continuance Commitment	Normative Commitment	Organizational Commitment
Adequate and Fair Compensation	Pearson Correlation	0.260**	-0.048	0.186**	0.189**
	Significance (2 – tailed)	0.000	0.237	0.000	0.000
	N	600	600	600	600
Safe and Healthy Working Conditions	Pearson Correlation	0.402**	0.041	0.443**	0.417**
	Significance (2 – tailed)	0.000	0.320	0.000	0.000
	N	600	600	600	600
Immediate Opportunity of Use and Develop Human Capacities	Pearson Correlation	0.229**	0.032	0.325**	0.274**
	Significance (2 – tailed)	0.000	0.441	0.000	0.000
	N	600	600	600	600
Future Opportunity for Continued Growth and Security	Pearson Correlation	0.077	-0.096	0.149**	0.056
	Significance (2 – tailed)	0.059	0.019	0.000	0.170
	N	600	600	600	600
Social Integration in Work Organization	Pearson Correlation	-0.026	-0.013	-0.019	-0.028
	Significance (2 – tailed)	0.531	0.757	0.642	0.500
	N	600	600	600	600
Constitutionalism in the Work Organization	Pearson Correlation	-0.063	-0.311**	-0.070	-0.218**
	Significance (2 – tailed)	0.120	0.000	0.088	0.000
	N	600	600	600	600
Work and the Total Life Space	Pearson Correlation	-0.162**	-0.095	-0.159**	-0.199**
	Significance (2 – tailed)	0.000	0.020	0.000	0.000
	N	600	600	600	600
Social Relevance of Work Life	Pearson Correlation	0.000	-0.057	0.063	0.000
	Significance (2 – tailed)	0.995	0.162	0.122	0.984
	N	600	600	600	600
Quality of Work Life	Pearson Correlation	0.167**	-0.134**	0.205**	0.107**
	Significance (2 – tailed)	0.000	0.001	0.000	0.008
	N	600	600	600	600

(** correlation is significant at the 0.01 level)

(Source: Primary data)

The above table 5 reveals that the correlation coefficient between quality of work life and organisational commitment is 0.107 which indicates 10.7% positive relationship exists between quality of work life and organisational commitment. Among three dimensions of organisational commitment two dimensions such as; affective commitment [$r = 0.167, p < 0.01$] and normative commitment [$r = 0.205, p < 0.01$] are also positively correlated with QWL. But correlation coefficient between continuance commitment and quality of work life is $-0.134 [p < 0.01]$ which indicates 13.4% negative relationship exists between quality of work life and continuance commitment. The Pearson's coefficient of correlation in all cases is significant at 1% level. Hence the null hypothesis is rejected and alternative hypothesis "there is significant relationship between quality of work life and organisational commitment" is accepted.

8. RESULTS AND INFERENCES

To investigate the relationship between quality of work life and organisational commitment of sales representatives in automobile industry Karl Pearson's Co-efficient of correlation was found for all the dimensions with factors of quality of work life. The results and inferences are discussed below.

- Statistical test proved that "there is significant relationship between quality of work life and organizational commitment".
- Positive relationship exists between quality of work life and organizational commitment.
- Affective commitment and normative commitment are also positively correlated with QWL. But there exists negative relationship between quality of work life and continuance commitment.

9. SUGGESTIONS

Based on the findings of the study the following suggestions are offered to achieve the improvement of quality of work life of sales representatives in automobile industry and thereby increasing the commitment of sales representatives.

- Majority of the sales representatives are afraid of certainty of their job in near future. If employees are not feeling security they may decide to quit the job. Therefore organizations must provide job security to the employees which enhance the level of job satisfaction among sales representatives. Job satisfaction leads to organizational commitment.
- For the growth of the organization it is advisable to maintain healthy relationship with sales representatives by merging the gap with communication, appreciating sales representatives for their performance, being friendly with sales representatives and respect them. This will bring a whole new motivation and organizational commitment.
- The organization should believe employees and give freedom to sales representatives to think, make decisions and act on behalf of the organization but within a set of guidelines within which they have to work.
- The management should allow employees to express their opinions on job and to express their grievances and should try to handle employee grievance.

10. CONCLUSION

A sales person is an intelligent agent who keeps the management informed of any significant development in his/her area, i.e., any strategic change of competitor etc. The power of Sales representatives in the continued success of an organization is not to be underestimated or under used. Thus sales representatives are very important to a company as they bridge gap between customer needs and the product/service provider. Sales people can make or break a business, depending on their level of professionalism, commitment and integrity. Sales representative's satisfaction and quality of work life directly affect company's ability to serve its customers.

The study results showed that when sales representatives are satisfied with quality of work life in the organisation, they will highly commit to the organisation. The success and growth of any industry depends on sales. Sales force is the backbone of all the businesses all over the world. Therefore, the people who do the selling are more important than any other group in the organisation. Despite their importance, most of the business strategies attribute least priority to the sales staff of the company. This leads to lower job satisfaction and sales performance, decreased organisational commitment and more turnovers.

REFERENCES

- [1] Allen and Meyer J.P (1990). "The measurement and antecedents of affective, continuance and normative commitment to the organization," *Journal of occupational psychology*, 23(5), 71-87.
- [2] Bal Shrikrishna (2009). "The Impact of Quality of Working Life on Job Performance and on Job Satisfaction of Employees." Thesis – University of Mumbai.
- [3] Charles E. Pettijohn, Linda S. Pettijohn, and A.J. Taylor (2007). "Does Salesperson Perception of the Importance of Sales Skills Improve Sales Performance, Customer Orientation, Job Satisfaction, and Organizational Commitment, and Reduce Turnover?" *Journal of Personal Selling & Sales Management*, 27:1, 75-88.
- [4] D.Gomathy (2013). "A Study on Organisational Stress, Emotional Intelligence and
- [5] Organisational Commitment among BPO Employees." Thesis - University Of Madras
- [6] Chennai.
- [7] Geethu Anna Mathew (2017). "Employee Training and Organisational Commitment-
- [8] A Study on Employees of Select Hotels in Kerala." Thesis - Mahatma Gandhi University.
- [9] G. Jagadeesh Chandran (2007). "Quality of Work Life in the Industrial Estates of Kerala." Thesis – Mahathma Gandhi University.
- [10] Hadi Farid, Zahri Izadi, Ismi Arif Ismail, Farhad Alipour (2014). "Relationship between quality of work life and organizational commitment among lecturers in a Malaysian public research university." *The Social Science Journal*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.soscij.2014.09.003>.
- [11] Henry Jonathan, Casius Darroux, Jared Massele (2013). "Perceived Job Satisfaction and its Impact on Organizational Commitment: An Empirical Study of Public Secondary School Teachers in Dodoma, Tanzania." *IOSR Journal of Business and Management (IOSR-JBM)* e-ISSN: 2278-487X, p-ISSN: 2319-7668. Volume 13, Issue 3 (Sep. - Oct. 2013), PP 41-52.
- [12] James A. Roberts, Kevin R. Coulson & Lawrence B. Chonko (1999). "Salesperson Perceptions of Equity and Justice and Their Impact on Organizational Commitment and Intent to Turnover." *Journal of Marketing Theory and Practice*, 7:1, pp 1-16, DOI:10.1080/10696679.1999.11501815.
- [13] J. Gnanayudam Ajantha Dharmasiri (2008). "The Influence of Quality of Work-life on Organizational Commitment : A Study of the Apparel Industry." *Sri Lankan Journal of Management*. Volume 13, Nos. 1 & 2.
- [14] Karen Seashore Louis (2006). "Effects of Teacher Quality of Work Life in Secondary Schools on Commitment and Sense of Efficacy." *School Effectiveness and School Improvement: An International Journal of Research, Policy and Practice*, 9:1, 1-27.
- [15] Madhu Anand and Dipti Arora (2009). "Burnout, Life Satisfaction and Quality of Life among Executives of Multi-National Companies." *Journal of the Indian Academy of Applied Psychology*, Vol. 35, No.1, pp 159-164.
- [16] Mark W. Johnston, P. Rajan Varadarajan, Charles M. Futrell, and Jeffrey Sager (1987). "The Relationship between Organizational Commitment, Job Satisfaction, and Turnover among New Salespeople." *Journal of Personal Selling & Sales Management*, 7:3, 29-38.
- [17] Normala and Daud (2010). "Investigating the Relationship between Quality of Work Life and Organizational Commitment amongst Employees in Malaysian Firms." *International Journal of Business and Management* Vol. 5, No. 10.
- [18] S. Kayalvizhi (2007). "A Study on Job Satisfaction, Organisational Commitment and Quality of Work Life among Private Hospital Nurses in Vellore District, Tamil Nadu- South India. Thesis – University of Madras.